

ELECTROACTIVE POLYMER AND ITS COMPOSITES: THEORY, EXPERIMENT AND APPLICATIONS

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1 General Introduction

Electroactive polymer (EAP) is one of the materials with special mechanical and electrical performance, which can generate several kinds of mechanical responses when exposed to an induced electric field. Dielectric elastomers (DEs), a type of electroactive polymer (EAP), are used to develop lightweight, low-cost, compliant actuators. This is due to its remarkable properties, for example, super large recoverable deformation, high energy density, high efficiency and high responsive speed [1]. They have attracted much attention in recent years. Their potential applications include smart space robotics, energy harvesters, Braille display medical devices, and area of aeronautics and astronautics. Dielectric elastomers work as a variable capacitor. When a potential is applied across the electrodes, the induced charge causes an electrostatic attraction between them. The electrical force between electrodes, also known as Maxwell stress, leads to a reduction in film thickness, which in turn results in elongation in the plane of the film. This paper reviews the theory, experiment and applications of electroactive polymer and its composites.

2 Electroactive polymer and its composites: theory

In order to offers great help in guiding design and fabrication of excellent actuators featuring dielectric elastomers, we investigate nonlinear mechanical performance, nonlinear dielectric performance, electromechanical stability, snap-through instability and failure of application devices of dielectric elastomer electroactive polymer soft materials its composites [2-8].

Our group used the elastic strain energy function with two material constants to analyze the stability performance of dielectric elastomers [6, 8]. The relationship between the nominal electric displacement and the nominal electric field of different dielectric elastomers is derived directly by using this model.

The free energy function of Mooney-Rivlin type dielectric elastomer is

$$W(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, D^-) = \frac{\mu}{2}(\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2 + \lambda_1^{-2}\lambda_2^{-2} - 3) + \frac{G}{2}(\lambda_1^{-2} + \lambda_2^{-2} + \lambda_1^2\lambda_2^2 - 3) + \frac{D^-^2}{2\varepsilon}\lambda_1^{-2}\lambda_2^{-2} \quad (1)$$

where μ and G are material constants determined by experiments. Evidently, the material constants are different for different dielectric elastomer materials (such as BJB TC-A/BC, HS3silicone, CF19-2186 silicone, VHB 4910). Pre-stretch uniformly the DE film, such that the stretch ratios in the two directions are equal, Let $\mu = kG$, where k is constant. The nominal stress and the nominal electric field respectively as follows:

$$\frac{D^-}{\sqrt{\varepsilon G}} = \sqrt{k(\lambda^6 - 1) + \lambda^8 - \lambda^2 - \frac{s}{G}\lambda^5} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{E^-}{\sqrt{G/\varepsilon}} = \sqrt{k(\lambda^{-2} - \lambda^{-8}) + 1 - \lambda^{-6} - \frac{s}{G}\lambda^{-3}} \quad (3)$$

When k is assigned different constants, the stability of DE materials can be analyzed by considering the pre-stretch ratio as variant. Figure 1 shows the

relationship between $\frac{D^-}{\sqrt{\varepsilon G}}$ and $\frac{E^-}{\sqrt{G/\varepsilon}}$ when $k=1$,

2, 2.5, and 5, respectively. In each case, $\frac{s}{G}$ takes

different values such as 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and E^- reaches its peak values. Before E^- reaches its peak value, the Hessian matrix is positive definite while after the peak value, the Hessian matrix is negative definite. Simply speaking, in the peak point, $\det(H)$

$=0$. As the value $\frac{s}{G}$ increases, the nominal electric field decreases under any constant k , which implies that increasing the prestretch ratio can improve the stability of the DE actuator.

Fig. 1. The nominal electric field v.s. the nominal electric displacement when the value k changes

An elastic strain energy function with two material constants was used to analyze the stability domain of dielectric elastomers by our group [7, 8]. The governing equations of the dielectric elastomer's stability are:

$$\begin{cases} y < \sqrt{k\lambda^8 + \lambda^6 - k\lambda^2 - 1} \\ y < \sqrt{(3k\lambda^8 + \lambda^6 + 3k\lambda^4 + 5)/3} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $y = D^-/\sqrt{\varepsilon C_1}$.

Figure 2 shows that for different value of k , the steady domain of dielectric elastomer is only below

both the two curves (the red and the blue lines, excluding these two curves), simultaneously, all other regions are instable.

Fig. 2. The steady domain of different dielectric elastomers (varying the value of k) subjected to special mechanical load ($\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda$) are illustrated: (a) $k=1$, (b) $k=1/2$, (c) $k=1/4$, (d) $k=1/5$

When the voltage ramps up, the membrane thins down, so that the same voltage will induce an even higher electric field. This positive feedback results in the pull-in instability [5]. The pull-in instability is commonly considered a mode of failure: the voltage causes the elastomer to reduce the thickness drastically, possibly leading to electrical breakdown. It is recognized recently, however, an elastomer may survive the pull-in instability without electrical breakdown, and be stabilized in a state of a much smaller thickness, resulting in the snap-through instability. This behavior is understood as follows. When the elastomer is subject to mechanical forces (Fig. 3a), on approaching the extension limit, λ_{lim} , the elastomer stiffens steeply. When the deformation is caused by voltage rather than the mechanical forces, the voltage-stretch curve is typically not monotonic (Fig. 3b). The voltage attains a local maximum at stretch λ_c , corresponding to the onset of the pull-in instability. As the voltage ramps up further, the membrane snaps, and is stabilized at a stretch close to λ_{lim} . Indeed, giant voltage-induced strains well above 100% are possible, so long as the elastomer snaps to a state safe from electrical breakdown.

We show that the snap-through instability can also be markedly affected by polarization saturation (Fig. 3c) [5]. When a dielectric with randomly oriented dipoles is subject to a voltage, the dipoles rotate to align with the electric field. The polarization of the material may saturate when the voltage is high enough. This nonlinear dielectric behavior will be incorporated in equations of state, and will be shown to modify the voltage-stretch curve.

Fig. 3. (a) Stress-stretch curve of a membrane of an elastomer under biaxial stresses. The curve stiffens steeply upon approaching the extension limit. (b) Voltage-stretch curve of a membrane of a dielectric elastomer is typically not monotonic. (c) For a dielectric contains randomly oriented dipoles, as the electric field increases, the dipoles rotate to align with the electric field, and the electric displacement saturates.

3 Electroactive polymer and its composites: experiment

Dielectric elastomers have shown good electromechanical performance. However, a considerably high activation electric field (on the order of 10^8 V/m) is required to achieve these levels, which limits the application of the dielectric elastomer. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the permittivity of dielectric elastomer composites. At present, there are mainly two ways to improve the permittivity of the dielectric elastomer composites: (1) ceramic particles with a high dielectric constant as filler are added, (2) conductive particles, such as carbon nanotube, carbon black, and short fiber are added. The BaTiO_3 based dielectric elastomer composite is fabricated and tested [4]. The stress-strain relationship, dielectric constant and the electro-induced deformation of carbon nanotube based dielectric elastomer composite are also demonstrated.

Figure 4 presents the dielectric spectroscopy of the composites from 100 to 10^7 Hz. Compared the two kinds of silicone composites (silicone/CB and silicone/CNT) to the pure silicone elastomer, we find that both the relative dielectric constant and dielectric loss increased to varying degrees.

Fig. 4. Dielectric spectroscopy of the composites from 100 to 10^7 Hz

4 Electroactive polymer and its composites: applications

Dielectric elastomer actuators, which can produce a stress-strain behavior, have shown great potential in mimicking the motion of natural muscle. These actuators are often named artificial muscles. We have fabricated the rolled, folded, inflated and stacked actuators of dielectric elastomer and their mechanical and electrical properties are also investigated.

The energy harvest device was designed and fabricated by our group [3], based on stacked dielectric elastomer actuators. As shown in Fig. 5, the waves can drive the buoy up and down, which will repetitively compress the stacked dielectric elastomer actuators. Hence, the conversion of mechanical energy to electrical energy is completed again and again. Braille display is one of the most important sensory functions for human perception of objects. Traditional refreshable Braille products are made from piezoelectric bimorph actuators. The complicated mechanical structure and high price of the piezoelectric Braille cells limit their further commercial application. Recently, dielectric elastomer actuators are used for refreshable Braille displays. In the 2010 smart structures/NDE conference, our group demonstrated their Braille devices, as seen in Fig. 6.

Fig. 5. Dielectric elastomer energy harvest device. Reprinted with permission from Reference 4. ©2010, American Institute of Physics.

Fig. 6. Dielectric elastomer Braille display. (a) setup (b) display

References

- [1] Z. G. Suo. "Theory of dielectric elastomers". *Acta Mechanica Sinica*. Vol. 23, No. 6, pp. 549-578, 2010.
- [2] YJ. Liu, LW. Liu, JS. Leng, K.Yu and SH. Sun. "electromechanical stability of dielectric elastomers". *Applied Physics Letters*, Vol. 94, No.21, p. 211901, 2009.
- [3] YJ. Liu, LW. Liu, Z. Zhang, Y. Jiao, SH. Sun and JS. Leng. "Analysis and manufacture of an energy harvester based on a Mooney-Rivlin-type dielectric elastomer". *Europhysics Letters*, Vol. 90, No. 03, p. 36004, 2010.
- [4] LW. Liu, YJ. Liu, Z. Zhang, B. Li and JS. Leng. "Electromechanical stability of electro-active silicone filled with high permittivity particles undergoing large deformation". *Smart Materials and Structures*, Vol. 19, No. 11, p. 115025, 2010.
- [5] B. Li, LW. Liu, ZG. Suo. "Extension limit, polarization saturation, and snap-through instability of dielectric elastomers". *International Journal of Smart and Nano Materials*, vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 59-67, 2011.
- [6] YJ. Liu, LW. Liu, Z. Zhang, L. Shi and JS. Leng. "Comment on "Method to analyze electromechanical stability of dielectric elastomers"", *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 93, p. 106101, 2008.
- [7] YJ. Liu, LW. Liu, L. Shi, SH. Sun and JS. Leng. "Comment "On electromechanical stability of dielectric elastomers [Appl. Phys. Lett. 93, 101902, 2008]"" *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 94, p. 096101, 2009.
- [8] JS. Leng, Alan K. T. Lau, SY. Du. *Multifunctional Polymer Nanocomposites*, CRC Press /Taylor & Francis, 2010.